

C++ Program for Sliding Vibration of Single Footings Located on Elastic Homogeneous Ground

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Abstract

Many techniques have been proposed to investigate sliding vibration of dynamically loaded single footings. The current study includes analysis of a rigid foundation resting on ground surface, when shear strain under dynamic loading is less than threshold strain and it is possible to consider the soil as an elastic material. Since calculation process takes a long time, an innovative C++ program was written as novelty of the paper. The results definitely demonstrate an appropriate consistency between program outputs and data reported in the past. Therefore, the executable C++ code can be employed to determine the sliding vibration amplitude of single foundations resting on a homogeneous elastic ground.

Keywords: Sliding vibration, Single footing, Vibration amplitude, Elastic Ground

1. Introduction

Appropriate design of shallow footings due to vibration is often based on displacement behaviour. Displacements under vibratory loading may be categorized as two main parts, including cyclic and permanent displacements. Elastic response of soil-footing system to vibrating loads and compaction of soil beneath the foundation lead to cyclic and permanent deformations, respectively. Vibration modes of a footing under the cyclic loading include vertical, yawing, lateral, pitching, longitudinal, rocking excitations [1, 2]. To date, many

analytical studies have been reported on footing vibration for various modes.

Analytical solutions for footings vibration has been presented by Wolf [3]. As an initial research, Lysmer and Richart [4] provided insight into dynamic behaviour of footings under vertical loading. Ahmadi and Seyedi [5] investigated the load transfer in mono-layered granular materials to study the effect of arching on dynamic grains discharge under vertical movement of trapdoor as a simulated underground structure. Jean et al. [6] explored system parameters of soil-footing interaction for time domain dynamic

analysis. Whitman and Richart [7] provided design procedures of dynamically loaded footings. Using in-situ experiments and laboratory results, Ajilchi et al. [2] proposed novel formulas to calculate the vertical vibration parameters of a rigid foundation located on elastic soil. Response of a foundation under various loading conditions has been published. For example, simple models for footings due to lateral and rocking motion has been proposed by Meek and Veletsos [8]. Foundation vibration has been assessed utilizing spring-dashpot-mass models [9] and consistent lumped-parameter models [10] using constitutive model such as Mohr-Coulomb criterion, which is used for arching phenomenon by Ahmadi and Seyedi [11]. In addition, Wolf [12] studied rough dynamic behaviour of embedded footing considering time domain analysis. The response of footings owing to torsion excitation has been studied by Veletsos and Nair [13]. The time domain response of frequency-dependent footing employing impedance functions has been evaluated by Safak [14]. Recently, Ardalan et al. [15] published innovative relationships among soil-foundation parameters for evaluation of rocking mode of footing vibration based on laboratory and at field data. Many attempts has been made to study the footing vibration under various conditions [16-19] that may be used for expanding the knowledge regarding the footing design aspects.

The present research investigates the sliding amplitude of vibration for a rigid single footing resting on surface of a homogeneous elastic ground under longitudinal and lateral excitations. A novel program* is developed in C++ language using Visual Studio 2010 software to simplify the corresponding calculation complexity. Creating C++ codes is a quick accurate approach to build an

* The executable file is available at <https://gofile.io/d/RuOfSb>
Please send your request via email to get password of .exe file.

effective instruction for economical design of footings under dynamic loading within a wide range of frequencies.

2. Principles of footing vibration

2-1-Vibration characteristics

Vibration modes are considered separately to make the analysis easy. Approximate mathematical models for assessment of displacement and rotation of footings under dynamic loads may be developed by treating the soil as a visco-elastic material. The main parameters for the vibration of footings may be calculated by considering the soil as a group of spring and dashpot which supports the foundation.

This work presents the fundamentals of horizontal vibration of single footings, located on an elastic homogeneous mono-layered ground. This medium that supports the footing and loads applied from the corresponding structure and earthquake motions is considered isotropic. Granular and cohesive soils show unique response against static or dynamic loading or local changes in particles, including arching as a result of load transfer [20, 21]. Hence, the actual behaviour of soil is significantly different from that of an elastic material, except for encountering low-level strains. This condition yields a rational estimation to treat soil as an elastic material.

2-2- Theoretical solution

A reliable approach was suggested by Lysmer and Richart [4], in which equivalent spring constant, k , and dashpot coefficient, c , were simply assigned as the main characteristics of the soil. The effect of dashpot coefficient on vibration assessment is commonly investigated by a parameter called damping ratio of the soil, D . Arnold et al. [22] assumed a rigid circular footing resting on a homogeneous layer of elastic soil as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Soil-foundation model under horizontal dynamic load (Courtesy of [4])

The sliding vibration amplitude owing to a dynamic constant force may be obtained as:

$$A_x = \frac{Q_0}{k_x} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left[1 - \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega_{nx}}\right)^2\right]^2 + 4D_x^2 \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega_{nx}}\right)^2}} \quad (1)$$

Similarly, rotating mass excitation leads to vibratory amplitude with a magnitude as:

$$A_x = \frac{m_1 e}{m} \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega_{nx}}\right)^2 \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left[1 - \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega_{nx}}\right)^2\right]^2 + 4D_x^2 \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega_{nx}}\right)^2}} \quad (2)$$

In equations (1) and (2):

$$\omega_{nx} = \sqrt{\frac{k_x}{m}} \quad (3)$$

$$k_x = \frac{32(1-\mu)G_{\max} r_0}{7-8\nu} \quad (4)$$

$$r_0 = \sqrt{\frac{BL}{\pi}} \quad (5)$$

$$D_x = \frac{C_x}{C_{cx}} \quad (6)$$

$$C_{cx} = \frac{18.4(1-\mu)}{7-8\mu} r_0^2 \sqrt{\rho G_{\max}} \quad (7)$$

Regarding the analytical solution proposed by Arnold et al. [22], variation of A_x with

ω/ω_n may be expected as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic plot of $A_x/(m_1 e/m)$ against ω/ω_n expected for sliding mode [1, 22]

3. Results and discussion

The C++ program is developed in 148 lines with Visual Studio 2010 software as given in Appendix. It provides calculation of sliding amplitude with any desired domains and intervals of vibration frequency. In other words, the program output is a set of data points that represents curve of footing vibration.

Figure 3 shows variation of dimensionless A_x with respect to $m_1 e/m$ parameter under dynamic loading induced by rotating mass against frequency ratio. The value of A_x increases first by increasing frequency until $\omega < \omega_{nx}$, whereas it decreases as frequency is increased when $\omega > \omega_{nx}$. It is also observed that increasing damping ratio decreases the maximum A_x and the peak value occurs at $\omega/\omega_{nx} = 1.0$, indicating the resonance state of vibration. For $\omega < 0.58\omega_{nx}$ and $\omega > 1.43\omega_{nx}$, A_x is almost low and independent of the external frequency.

Figure 3: Dimensionless $A_x/(m_1e/m)$ versus ω/ω_{nx} obtained from C++ program output

Figure 3 clearly proves accuracy of the code due to the close similarity of curve trend to the plot expected by Arnold et al. [22], that demonstrates the high effectiveness of the developed C++ program.

It should be noted that the $A_x-\omega/\omega_{nx}$ graph possesses a point of discontinuity at $\omega/\omega_{nx}=1.0$ which can be determined using L'Hôpital's rule [23, 24]. It provides a technique to evaluate limits of indeterminate forms. Application of the rule often converts an indeterminate form to an expression, which may be easily evaluated by substitution. Therefore, the value of A_x at $\omega/\omega_{nx}=1.0$ based on dynamic loading source may be calculated by following equations:

$$A_{x(peak)} = \frac{Q_0}{k_x} \frac{1}{2D_x \sqrt{1-D_x^2}}; \text{ (Constant force)} \quad (8)$$

$$A_{x(peak)} = \frac{m_1 e}{m} \frac{1}{2D_x \sqrt{1-D_x^2}}; \text{ (Rotating mass)} \quad (9)$$

A wide range of damping ratio values may be used for achieving an exact analysis. Table 1 summarizes the characteristics of four actual projects of shallow concrete

footing with 25 MPa compressive strength to assess the program accuracy.

Table 1: Properties of soil-foundation system under constant force dynamic load (adopted from [1, 19])

Soil type	Footing geometry		Horizontal dynamic load			Soil properties	
	B (m)	L (m)	r_0 (m)	Q_0 (kN)	f (Hz)	ω (rad/s)	ρ (kg/m ³) ν
Dense sand	1	2	0.80	70	0-5	0-31.42	1475 0.25
Medium clay	1	2	0.80	70	0-5	0-31.42	1620 0.35
Dense sand	2	3	1.38	110	0-8	0-50.26	1475 0.25
Medium clay	2	3	1.38	110	0-8	0-50.26	1620 0.35

Typical variations of A_x against ω listed above for medium clay and dense sand with various damping ratio values are illustrated in Figure 4. For both sandy and clayey ground beneath the footing, increasing the frequency of external dynamic loads reduces the horizontal displacement of foundation.

Figure 4: Variation of A_x with ω for research soils under constant force excitation produced by C++ program

The ω_{nx} is calculated as 307 rad/s and 228 rad/s for medium clay and dense sand, respectively. In addition, the $A_{x(\text{peak})}$ values are evaluated 2.81×10^{-4} m and 1.88×10^{-4} m for grounds with medium clay and dense sand, respectively.

The figure indicates that a shallow footing resting on medium clay undergoes larger vibration in sliding mode compared to that on dense sand. This may be interpreted by means of soil stiffness and shear strength parameters such that clay conventionally has larger G and τ_f than sand. Hence, for the same conditions clay transmits greater energy from earthquake to the footing in comparison to sand. On the other hand, granular material has no cohesion factor according to Mohr-Coulomb failure theory [25-29] and damps the earthquake vibration more than cohesive soils. The C++ program also covers calculation of discontinuity points of vibration curve, which results in serious problem for correct prediction of sliding amplitude [30-32].

Using the generated C++ program can be extended into many conditions and consequently, it leads to an optimum design of single footing. The whole C++ program and the consequent calculations are the novelties of this research and have not been reported before. However, it is advisable to be employed in evaluation of the sliding vibration for many other concrete shallow foundations for validation of the program outputs.

5. Conclusion

The accurate analysis of dynamically loaded footing vibration is a significant challenge from both theoretical and practical projects.

Lots of studies have concentrated on finding the simplified models to simulate vibration of shallow footings resting on surface of homogeneous ground within elastic stress-strain. However, to the best of the authors' knowledge, no frequency domain solution has been available to calculate the exact value of vibration amplitude owing to horizontal excitation. The current paper presented a novel approach to predict the sliding vibration amplitude of a shallow foundation within a wide range of loading frequencies. To this purpose, a new robust program was developed in C++ language with 148 lines using Visual Studio 2010 software based on a theory proposed by Arnold et al [22]. The key findings are summarized as follows.

- (1) The A_x increases first by increasing load frequency until $\omega < \omega_{nx}$, whereas it decreases as frequency is increased when $\omega > \omega_{nx}$.
- (2) For the same conditions, increasing the damping ratio of soil results in the A_x reduction.
- (3) The $A_{x(\text{peak})}$ takes place at resonance state, *i.e.* when $\omega/\omega_{nx}=1.0$ corresponding to discontinuity point of vibration curve.
- (4) For $\omega < 0.58\omega_{nx}$ and $\omega > 1.43\omega_{nx}$, the A_x is significantly small and independent of the external loading frequency.
- (5) For both sandy and clayey ground, increasing the frequency of dynamic loads reduces horizontal displacement of footing.
- (6) The written C++ program is capable of being modified for many problems to determine other modes of footing vibration modes so that an optimum design of single footings is achieved.

Notation

A_x = Amplitude of sliding vibration

$A_{x(\text{peak})}$ = Maximum amplitude of sliding vibration

Q_0 = Magnitude of constant force

k_x = Spring constant of soil in horizontal direction

ω = Circular frequency of loading

ω_n = Natural circular frequency of system

ω_{nx} = Natural circular frequency of system in sliding

f = Frequency of system

f_{nx} = Natural frequency of system

C_x = Damping in sliding

C_{cx} = Critical damping in sliding

D_x = Damping ratio of soil in horizontal direction

B = Width of a rectangular footing

L = Length of a rectangular footing

r_0 = Circle radius equivalent to a rectangular footing

m = Foundation mass

m_1 = Total rotating mass causing excitation

e = Eccentricity of each rotating mass

μ = Poisson's ratio of soil

ρ = Density of soil

G = Shear modulus of soil

G_{max} = Maximum shear modulus of soil

τ_f = Shear strength of soil

Appendix: C++ Program

```
1. #include <iostream>
2. #include <cmath>
3. #include <iomanip>
4. #include <fstream>
5. using namespace std;
6. int main()
7. {
8.     start:
9.     char ans,y,n,exc;
10.    float c,k,m,mu,G,B,L,ro,q0,m1,e,wf,i,no;
11.    float dmpr,kx,cx,fn,bx,r0,dx,wnx,w,axresf,axresm,axresfno,axresmno,dt;
12.    cout << "Analysis for Sliding Vibration of Foundation : "<<endl;
13.    cout<<" Input c (Ns/m) : ";cin>>c;
14.    cout<<" Input k (N/m) : ";
15.    cin>>k;
16.    cout<<" Input m (kg) : ";
17.    cin>>m;
18.    dmpr=((0.5*c)/(sqrt(k*m)));
19.    cout<<" The damping ratio is : "<< dmpr <<endl;
20.    cin.ignore();
21.    cout<<" The damping Condition is : ";
22.    if ( dmpr < 1 ) {
23.        cout<<"Under Damped"<<endl;
24.        goto Analysis;
25.    }
26.    else if ( dmpr > 1 ) {
27.        cout<<"Over Damped"<<endl;
28.        cout<<"No Vibration Occurred"<<endl;
29.        cout<<"Do You Want to Continue ? (Yes: y - No: n) "<<endl;
30.        cin>>ans;
31.        if ( ans == 'y' ) {
32.            goto start;
33.        }
34.        if ( ans == 'n' ) {
35.            cout<<"Thank You for Using This Program !"<<endl;
36.            system ("pause");
37.            return 0;
38.        }
39.    }
40.    else {
41.        cout<<"Critical Damped"<<endl;
42.        cout<<"No Vibration Occurred"<<endl;
43.        cout<<"Do You Want to Continue ? (Yes: y - No: n) "<<endl;
44.        cin>>ans;
45.        if ( ans == 'y' ) {
46.            goto start;
47.        }
48.        if ( ans == 'n' ) {
```

```
49. cout<<"Thank You for Using This Program !"<<endl;
50. system ("pause");
51. return 0;
52. }
53. }
54. cout<<"-----"<<endl;
55. Analysis:
56. cout<<" Input B (m) : ";
57. cin>>B;
58. cout<<" Input L (m) : ";
59. cin>>L;
60. r0=sqrt((B*L)/3.141592654);
61. cout<<" The r0 (m) is : "<<r0<<endl;
62. cout<<" Input G (Pa): ";
63. cin>>G;
64. cout<<" Input mu : ";
65. cin>>mu;
66. cout<<" Input ro (kg/m3) : ";
67. cin>>ro;
68. kx=(32*(1-mu)*G*r0)/(7-8*mu);
69. cx=(18.4*(1-mu)*pow(r0, 2)*sqrt(ro*G))/(7-8*mu);
70. fn=(0.5/3.141592654)*sqrt(kx/m);
71. bx=((7-8*mu)*m)/(32*(1-mu)*ro*pow(r0, 3));
72. dx=c/cx;
73. wnx=sqrt(kx/m);
74. cout<<" The kx is (N/m) : "<<kx<<endl;
75. cout<<" The Ccx is (Ns/m) : "<<cx<<endl;
76. cout<<" The fn is (Hz) : "<<fn<<endl;
77. cout<<" The Bx is : "<<bx<<endl;
78. cout<<" The Dx is : "<<dx<<endl;
79. cout<<" The wnx (rad/s) is : "<<wnx<<endl;
80. cout<<" Resonance Occurred? (Yes: y - No: n) ";
81. cin>>ans;
82. if ( ans == 'y' ) {
83. cout<<" Excitation Type ? (Constant Force: f - Rotation Mass: r) ";
84. cin>>exc;
85. if ( exc == 'f' ) {
86. cout<<" Input Q0 (N) : ";
87. cin>>q0;
88. axresf=(q0/kx)/(2*dx*sqrt(1-dx*dx));
89. cout<<" The Ax[res] (m) is : "<<axresf<<endl;
90. }
91. else if ( exc == 'r' ) {
92. cout<<" Input m1 (kg) : ";
93. cin>>m1;
94. cout<<" Input e (m) : ";
95. cin>>e;
96. axresm=((m1*e)/m)/(2*dx*sqrt(1-dx*dx));
97. cout<<" The Ax[res] (m) is : "<<axresm<<endl;
98. }
```

```
99. }
100. else if ( ans == 'n' ) {
101. cout<<" Input minimum w (rad/s) : ";
102. cin>>w;
103. cout<<" Input maximum w (rad/s) : ";
104. cin>>wf;
105. cout<<" Input desired number of curve points : ";
106. cin>>no;
107. dt=(wf-w)/(no-1);
108. cout<<" Excitation Type ? (Constant Force: f - Rotation Mass: r) ";
109. cin>>exc;
110. if ( exc == 'f' ) {
111. cout<<" Input Q0 (N) : ";
112. cin>>q0;
113. cout << left << setw(14) << "wi" << left << "Axi (m)"<<endl;
114. for(i=w; i<=wf; i+=dt){
115. axresfno=(q0/kx)/sqrt(pow((1-(i/wnx)*(i/wnx)), 2)+4*pow((dx*i)/wnx, 2));
116. cout<<left<<setw(14)<<i<<left<<axresfno<<endl;
117. }
118. ofstream myfile;
119. myfile.open ("Analysis\\Result.txt");
120. myfile<<"wi,Axi (m)"<<endl;
121. for(i=w; i<=wf; i+=dt){
122. axresfno=(q0/kx)/sqrt(pow((1-(i/wnx)*(i/wnx)), 2)+4*pow((dx*i)/wnx, 2));
123. myfile<<i<<","<<axresfno<<endl;
124. }
125. }
126. else if ( exc == 'r' ) {
127. cout<<" Input m1 (kg) : ";
128. cin>>m1;
129. cout<<" Input e (m) : ";
130. cin>>e;
131. cout << left << setw(14) << "wi" << left << "Axi (m)"<<endl;
132. for(i=w; i<=wf; i+=dt){
133. axresmno=((m1*e)/m)*pow(i/wnx, 2)/sqrt(pow((1-(i/wnx)*(i/wnx)), 2)+4*pow((dx*i)/wnx, 2));
134. cout<<left<<setw(14)<<i<<left<<axresmno<<endl;
135. }
136. ofstream myfile;
137. myfile.open ("Analysis\\Result.txt");
138. myfile<<"wi,Axi (m)"<<endl;
139. for(i=w; i<=wf; i+=dt){
140. axresmno=((m1*e)/m)*pow(i/wnx, 2)/sqrt(pow((1-(i/wnx)*(i/wnx)), 2)+4*pow((dx*i)/wnx, 2));
141. myfile<<i<<","<<axresmno<<endl;
142. }
143. }
144. }
145. system("PAUSE");
146. goto start;
147. return 0;
148. }
```

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